

1,3-Diazetidin-2-Ones: Synthetic Approaches and Therapeutic Promise within the Aza- β -Lactam Family

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Dedicated with profound respect to Professor Milan Potáček on the occasion of his 80th birthday

1,3-diazetid-2-ones, overlooked members of the aza- β -lactam family, are structurally distinct four-membered nitrogen-containing heterocycles with strong potential in medicinal chemistry, particularly as β -lactamase inhibitors and antibiotic analogues. This review provides a comprehensive overview of their synthesis, structural diversity, and biological significance. The most established synthetic method is the [2 + 2] cycloaddition between C=N nucleophiles and isocyanates, though this approach is highly substrate dependent and frequently leads to side products or cycloreversion. Alternative strategies—including photochemical and

organometallic methodologies—have been explored but remain limited in scope. As a result, access to 1,3-diazetid-2-ones is significantly constrained, impeding wider investigation and application. In silico studies suggest favorable stability and reactivity profiles and indicate these compounds could circumvent β -lactam resistance through hydrolysis-resistant enzyme intermediates. Several derivatives have demonstrated promising antibacterial, antifungal, antioxidant, and anticancer activities. Nevertheless, further synthetic innovation is essential to fully realize the therapeutic potential of this underexplored class of heterocycles.

1. Introduction

Four-membered nitrogen-containing heterocycles^[1–3] play a pivotal role in both synthetic chemistry and medicinal applications. Among these, β -lactams^[4,5] stand out as the cornerstone of some of the most widely used antibiotics,^[6,7] including penicillins, cephalosporins, monobactams, and carbapenems. The discovery and development of penicillin revolutionized modern medicine by providing an effective treatment for bacterial infections and ushering in the antibiotic era. However, the growing threat of antibiotic resistance—particularly via β -lactamase enzymes—has driven the search for novel scaffolds capable of retaining or enhancing the therapeutic efficacy of classical β -lactams.^[8,9]

In this context, aza- β -lactams have emerged as promising structural analogues.^[10,11] These compounds feature an additional nitrogen atom within the four-membered ring, potentially conferring improved stability and resistance to enzymatic hydrolysis. Over the past 40 years, considerable research has focused on the synthesis and evaluation of 1,2-diazetid-3-ones^[12] as β -lactam analogues,^[13] leaving other aza- β -lactam variants—such as 1,3-diazetid-2,4-diones,^[14–16] imino-1,3-diazetid-2-ones,^[17,18] and 1,3-diazetid-2,4-diimines^[19–22]—relatively underexplored. Notably, despite their predicted potential as the most promising aza- β -lactam candidates for overcoming β -lactamase-mediated resistance,^[23–25] investigations into 1,3-diazetid-2-ones have remained limited. This is

presumably due to the synthetic challenges associated with accessing this class of compounds, which restrict their broader application and study.

In this review, we focus on 1,3-diazetid-2-ones, summarizing the current state of knowledge regarding their synthesis, their potential role in addressing antibiotic resistance, and prospective strategies to overcome the limitations of existing methodologies (Figure 1).

2. Synthesis

2.1. Thermal [2 + 2] Cycloaddition

The earliest attempts to synthesize 1,3-diazetid-2-ones (3) date back to the early second half of the 20th century and are closely associated with the rise of cycloaddition chemistry. Unsurprisingly, the pioneering work in this area was carried out by Huisgen,^[26] Richter,^[27] and Ullrich,^[28] who independently investigated the reactions of isocyanates (2) with molecules bearing C=N functional groups (1). Since then, the [2 + 2] cycloaddition strategy has remained the most extensively studied approach for constructing the 1,3-diazetid-2-one (3) molecular scaffold. This method typically involves a cycloaddition reaction between a nucleophilic C=N functionality (1)—such as those found in imines, amidines, imino ethers, or guanidines—and an electrophilic C=N functionality (2), commonly present in aryl or alkyl isocyanates (Scheme 1).

However, despite its apparent simplicity, [2 + 2] cycloaddition does not always yield the desired 1,3-diazetid-2-ones (3). In many cases, it leads—partially or exclusively—to undesired side products formed via ring opening of the 1,3-diazetid-2-one and subsequent reactions of the resulting acyclic intermediates. The outcome of the reaction strongly depends on the nature of the C=N nucleophile employed. Therefore, in the following sections, we will discuss each class of substrates and their corresponding products separately.

2.1.1. Reaction of Imines with Isocyanates and Reaction Mechanism

As previously mentioned, one of the first contributions to this field was made by Richter in 1968 (Scheme 2).^[29] Notably, even

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Figure 1. A) Structure of a typical β -lactam-containing antibiotic (penicillin) alongside potential aza analogues: the well-established 1,2-diazetidion-3-one scaffolds^[12] and the underexplored 1,3-diazetidion-2-ones. B) Subclasses of 1,3-diazetidion-2-ones featuring an sp^2 -hybridized carbon at the C4 position, which have primarily found applications in coordination and polymer chemistry.

Scheme 1. A summary of synthetic approaches to 1,3-diazetidion-2-ones through [2 + 2] cycloaddition, highlighting the range of suitable substrates.

in his initial study, it was observed that the [2 + 2] cycloaddition of aldimines (4) and ketoimines (5) with aryl isocyanate (6) did not yield identical products. Moreover, the reactions produced not only the desired 1,3-diazetidion-2-one (7) in the case of aldimines, or the undesired triazinane-2,4-dione (8) in the case of ketoimines, but also a variety of side products.

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Scheme 2. A) Solvent-free [2 + 2] cycloaddition reactions of aldimines and B) ketoimines with aryl isocyanates 6 that yields 1,3-diazetidion-2-one 7 or triazinane-2,4-dione 8 skeletons.

In summary, Richter observed that only electron-rich aldimines 4 afforded 1,3-diazetidion-2-ones 7, albeit in low yields (5–11%) when methoxy-substituted phenyl aldimine 4 was used. In contrast, the presence of a dimethylamino substituent significantly improved the yield, reaching up to 85%. The use of isocyanates 6 bearing electron-withdrawing groups (EWGs) also had a positive effect on the reaction yields. On the other hand, when sterically more demanding ketoimines 5 were employed, no diazetidinone products were obtained under the reaction conditions. The only isolable products were triazinane-2,4-diones 8, which were identified as ring-opening/[4 + 2]-cycloaddition products of the initially formed diazetidinones with a second

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molecule of isocyanate **6**. These findings spurred further interest in elucidating the reaction mechanism,^[30] leading to the isolation and structural characterization of several reaction intermediates. A comprehensive and intensive experimental investigation ultimately led to a proposed reaction mechanism, which was later supported—three decades afterward—by detailed ab initio studies.^[31]

The generally accepted reaction mechanism of dialkyl ketimine **1** with alkyl isocyanate **2** is illustrated in **Scheme 3**. The reaction proceeds via a stepwise mechanism. In the first step, the nucleophilic lone pair on the C=N bond of compound **1** adds onto the electrophilic carbon of isocyanate **2**. The resulting adduct **9** can be represented by four resonance structures (**9A–9D**).

From a reactivity perspective, two pairs of resonance structures can be considered. The first pair, **9A** and **9B**, features a negative charge on the oxygen atom derived from the isocyanate and a positive charge either on the nitrogen (**9A**) or the carbon (**9B**) of the original C=N group. This charge distribution suggests the potential formation of oxazetid-2-imine-like species **10** via intramolecular cyclization. However, despite being kinetically feasible, no such products have been observed, indicating that this pathway is disfavored under the reaction conditions.

The second pair, **9C** and **9D**, features a negative charge on the nitrogen atom originating from the isocyanate and differs in the location of the positive charge on the atoms of starting imine C=N (on nitrogen in **9C**, on carbon in **9D**). Based on orbital geometry and computational studies, **9D** appears to best

represent the charge distribution responsible for further reactivity.^[31] This includes intramolecular cyclization to form the desired 1,3-diazetid-2-one **3** (Scheme 3, deep blue arrows) and undesired intermolecular [4 + 2] cycloadditions with either starting material—compound **1** (orange arrows) or **2** (light blue arrows).

The intramolecular cyclization to form **3** is likely the fastest transformation. However, under typical [2 + 2] cycloaddition conditions, it can also undergo rapid cycloreversion. This reversion may regenerate the original zwitterionic intermediate **9** (breaking along the red bond) or cleave along the former C=N σ -bond (bond highlighted in yellow), yielding zwitterionic intermediate **11C**. Although four resonance forms of **11** can be drawn (analogous to **9**), they are omitted here for clarity. Intermediates **9** and **11** differ only in the substitution pattern on the nitrogen atom (blue and orange substituents on nitrogen atoms are exchanged). This change in substitution pattern becomes evident through side reactions of **9** and **11** with isocyanate **2** (light blue) or imine **1** (orange). These lead to the formation of 1,3,5-triazin-2-one **12** (from imines) or 1,3,5-triazinane-2,4-dione **13** (from isocyanates), each with distinct substitution patterns on nitrogen atoms. Additionally, intermediate **11** is in equilibrium with imine **14** and isocyanate **15** (shown in grey), both of which can re-enter the reaction network as substrates for either [2 + 2] or [4 + 2] cycloadditions.

Unsurprisingly, the reaction outcome depends on the stereo-electronic properties of the substrates, which influence the rates of intramolecular (retro)cyclization (deep blue) and intermolecular [4 + 2] cycloadditions. Reaction stoichiometry also plays a key

Scheme 3. Proposed reaction mechanism for the stepwise [2 + 2] cycloaddition between compounds **1** and **2**, leading to 1,3-diazetid-2-one (**3**): complete overview. The scheme illustrates all potential (e.g., formation of adduct **10**, indicated by a red arrow) and observed products: the desired 1,3-diazetid-2-one (**3**, in deep blue), 1,3,5-triazin-2-one (**12**, in light blue), and 1,3,5-triazinane-2,4-dione (**13**, in orange), along with additional intermediates. In compound **3**, the red bond represents the newly formed bond during the transformation of intermediate **9** into product **3**. A competitive retrocyclization pathway, involving cleavage of the bond highlighted in yellow, leads to intermediate **11**.

role: an imine/isocyanate ratio of 2:1 favors formation of **12**, while a 1:2 ratio favors **13**. Notably, under appropriate conditions and with suitable substituents on imine **1**, zwitterionic intermediate **9** can be isolated.^[32,33]

With the proposed reaction mechanism in mind, the outcomes observed from reactions between variously substituted imines and isocyanates can be readily rationalized. Chronologically, this discussion begins with the work of Arbuzov, who in the early 1970s investigated the reactions of aromatic imines (Schiff bases) **14** with acyl isocyanates **15** (Scheme 4).^[34]

Arbuzov and his co-workers observed that treating equimolar amounts of imine **14** and acyl isocyanate **15** led to two competing cycloaddition pathways: a [2 + 2] cycloaddition yielding diazetidinone **17** and a [4 + 2] cycloaddition forming 1,3,5-oxadiazin-4-one **18** (Scheme 4A).^[35] Prolonged reaction times and elevated temperatures favored the formation of the [4 + 2] cycloadduct. Furthermore, aryl imines **14** bearing electron-donating groups (EDGs) promoted the formation of diazetidinones **17**, whereas imines substituted with EWGs favored the formation of the six-membered 1,3,5-oxadiazin-4-one **18**. This trend is attributed to the stabilization of the intermediate dipole **16** by EWGs, or its destabilization by EDGs, as illustrated by resonance forms **16A** and **16B**. The yield of diazetidinones **17** could be further improved by replacing the nonpolar solvent CCl₄ with a more polar solvent such as diethyl ether, which enhances solvation of the acyl group's oxygen atom and thereby reduces its nucleophilicity. Conversely, when trichloroacetyl-substituted isocyanate **15** was employed, the increased stabilization of intermediate dipole **16** (resonance form **16B**) led to the preferential formation of 1,3,5-oxadiazin-4-one **18** as the major product under thermodynamic conditions (compounds **18h–18i**).

In contrast, when imine **14** was reacted with an excess of acyl isocyanate **15** (2.0 equivalents) in polar solvents such as DMSO or liquid SO₂, the reaction exclusively yielded 1,3,5-triazinane-2,4-dione **19** (Scheme 4B).

Only recently, motivated by their interest in aza- β -lactam analogues of meropenem, Altmann and co-workers investigated the synthesis of diazetidinones **23** (Scheme 5A).^[35] Following an approach analogous to that of Arbuzov,^[36] they examined the reaction of acyl isocyanates **21** with imines **20**. The key distinction between the two approaches lies in the nature of the imines: while Arbuzov employed imines derived from aromatic aldehydes and anilines, Altmann used imines generated from *O*-allylated glycine and aliphatic aldehydes. This seemingly subtle variation proved to be critical. In all cases examined, the desired four-membered diazetidinones **23** were not formed. Instead, a competing intramolecular *O*-cyclization occurred, yielding six-membered 1,3,5-oxadiazin-4-ones **24**—the same side product observed by Arbuzov nearly 50 years earlier. It was reasoned that the steric hindrance introduced by the gem-dimethyl group in imine **20** might be responsible for the observed lack of reactivity toward [2 + 2] cycloaddition. Unfortunately, the use of a monomethylated analogue, **25**, led only to a competing [1,5]-hydrogen shift, resulting in the formation of *N*-vinyl urea derivative **27**, which underwent hydrolysis during workup to give acyl urea **28** (Scheme 5B).

Attempts to access diazetidinone **32** via an alternative strategy, involving base-promoted intramolecular 4-exo-trig cyclization of amide **30**, were also unsuccessful (Scheme 5C).

Finally, it is worth noting that in 1987, Braña and co-workers reported an unexpected product while studying the preparation of hydantoins from *L*-tryptophans **33** and alkyl isocyanates **35** (Scheme 6).^[37,38] The initially isolated compound **36** was originally assigned a structure featuring a four-membered diazetidinone ring. However, subsequent studies by Claesson^[39] revealed that the compound was, in fact, a five-membered oxazolidin-5-one **37**. This revised structural assignment was later confirmed by X-ray crystallography.^[40]

Finally, Pd-mediated [2 + 2] cycloaddition reactions were also investigated *in silico* by Novikov.^[41] However, none of the proposed approaches—either activation of the isocyanate-reacting partner (intermediate **38**) or the imine (intermediate **39**)—were found to be conclusive, and the formation of 1,3-diazetidino-3-ones **3** via this pathway was ruled out (Scheme 7).

2.1.2. Reaction of Amidines and Imino Ethers and with Isocyanates

In addition to the widely studied C=N group of imines, amidines, and imino ethers (Scheme 1) have also attracted scientific interest. In this context, Arbuzov and Zbova made a pioneering contribution by investigating the reactivity of cyclic amidines **42** (Scheme 8).^[36] Their reaction with acyl isocyanates **15** led to the formation of spirocyclic heterocycles **44** in yields ranging from 48 to 61%.

In 1973, Seckinger^[42] investigated the cycloaddition of methyl or aryl isocyanates **35** with various formamidines **45** (Scheme 9A). Although the formation of diazetidinones **46** was detected using IR spectroscopy, the desired compounds could not be isolated in any of the attempted cases, presumably due to their instability. A rapid retro-[2 + 2] cycloaddition is believed to occur instead.

However, when an excess of isocyanates **35** was used (Scheme 9B), triazines **47**—the products of dipolar reaction intermediate addition to isocyanate—were successfully isolated in good yields.

An even more intriguing outcome was observed when hydrazine-derived amidine **48** was used as an equivalent of formamidines **45** (Scheme 10).^[43] In this case, the retro-[2 + 2] cycloreversion yielded not only the starting materials **48** and **35** but also alternative cycloreversion products **52** and **53**. The isocyanate derivative **52** then further reacted with an excess of isocyanate **35**, forming the stable zwitterionic salt **55** in very good yields.

Kratz described the reaction of ϵ -caprolactam-derived imine ether **56a** with aryl isocyanates **6** at room temperature (Scheme 11A).^[44] Although the reaction typically requires \approx 20 days to reach completion, it proceeds with high efficiency, yielding diazetidinones **57** as the exclusive products in excellent yields. However, the isolated diazetidinones **57** were found to be thermally unstable and undergo rapid retroaddition upon heating.

A. Reaction of imines with 1.0 equiv of acyl isocyanate

B. Reaction of imines with 2.0 equiv of acyl isocyanate

Scheme 4. Reaction of acyl isocyanates **15** with imines **14**. A) Products formed when the reaction is carried out using a 1:1 equimolar ratio of starting materials. B) Products formed when the reaction is carried out with a 1:2 ratio of imine to isocyanate.

Scheme 5. A) Attempted [2 + 2] cycloaddition-based synthesis of diazetidinones **23**, which instead yielded [4 + 2] cycloaddition products—six-membered 1,3-oxadiazin-4-ones **24**. B) Attempted [2 + 2] cycloaddition using less sterically hindered imines **25**, resulting in an unexpected [1,5]-hydrogen shift and formation of N-vinyl urea derivative **27**. C) Unsuccessful synthesis of diazetidinone **32** via a base-promoted intramolecular 4-exo-trig cyclization strategy. *alloc* = *N*-allyloxycarbonyl.

Scheme 6. The proposed synthesis of diazetidinones **36** based on a [2 + 2] cycloaddition reaction between *L*-tryptophan derivatives **34** and alkyl isocyanates **35** and the revised structure of obtained products (**37**).

In contrast, when smaller-ring imine ethers **56b** and **56c** are reacted with aryl isocyanates **6**, the starting imine ether **56** undergoes in situ isomerization to the corresponding enamine (Scheme 11B).^[45] The only isolated product in these cases is compound **58**, resulting from the addition of the enamine to the isocyanate (Scheme 11C).

Interestingly, the imine–enamine equilibrium was also observed in the case of ϵ -caprolactam-derived diazetidinones **57**. When compound **57** is subjected to elevated temperatures

in the presence of an excess of isocyanate, rapid retrocyclization occurs. The resulting lactam-based imine ether subsequently isomerizes to the corresponding enamine, and the only isolated products from such reactions are pyrimidinoazepines.^[46]

Based on current knowledge and available examples, it is reasonable to assume that the reaction mechanism established for the [2 + 2] cycloaddition of imines (see Section 2.1.1) also applies when amidines and imine ethers are used as imine equivalents in similar [2 + 2] cycloaddition reactions. However, the presence of

Scheme 7. Pd-mediated [2 + 2] cycloaddition of imine **1** and isocyanate **2** investigated by in silico means.

Scheme 8. Synthesis of spirocyclic heterocycles **44** starting from amidine **42**.

an additional external lone pair—either on a nitrogen or oxygen atom—within the resulting diazetidinone ring appears to play a critical role in determining the stability of the four-membered products. Obtained results strongly suggest that the thermal instability of these compounds arises from a destabilizing interaction between the lone pair on nitrogen or oxygen and the antibonding σ^*_{C-N} orbital within the diazetidinone ring (Figure 2). This interaction facilitates decomposition under elevated temperatures.

It is therefore not surprising that the only isolable and relatively stable diazetidinones derived from amidines and imine ethers are those in which the [2 + 2] cycloaddition yields bicyclic products. In such cases, the lone pairs on the exocyclic nitrogen or oxygen atoms are geometrically misaligned and thus unable to effectively interact with the antibonding σ^*_{C-N} orbitals of the diazetidinone ring, thereby enhancing the stability of the resulting compounds.

2.1.3. Reaction of Guanidines with Isocyanates

Compared to all other C=N functional group reagents described previously, guanidines (**59**) react due to their higher nucleophilicity

rapidly with isocyanates (**60**) (Scheme 12). The first documented reaction of guanidines (**59**) with isocyanates was reported by Ulrich and co-workers in 1968 (Scheme 12A).^[28] In this study, *n*-butyl and phenyl guanidines (**59a** and **59b**, respectively) were reacted with 4-toluenesulfonyl isocyanate (**60a**) in benzene at room temperature. The reaction proceeded instantaneously, affording the desired diazetidinones (**61a** and **61b**) in excellent yields. However, once isolated in pure form, the diazetidinones underwent rapid cycloreversion even at low temperatures (0 °C), yielding stable tosylated guanidines (**62**) and the corresponding isocyanates (**63**). Clean decomposition of **61**, **62**, and **63** could also be achieved by prolonging the reaction time, making this transformation particularly suitable for the synthesis of various isocyanates.

A similar approach to guanidine-derived diazetidinones was employed by Schaumann and co-workers.^[32,47] In their study, guanidines (**59**) were reacted with sulfonyl or acyl isocyanates (**60**) in ether at room temperature. Interestingly, in some cases, the primary product of the stepwise [2 + 2] cycloaddition, compound **64**, could be isolated due to its low solubility in ether. Its structure was confirmed by X-ray crystallography and NMR spectroscopy. In contrast, diazetidinones (**61c** and **61d**) could not be isolated, and no traces of these compounds were detected in the reaction mixture. Their formation was inferred indirectly from the presence of the decomposition products—guanidines (**62**) and isocyanates (**63**).

In summary, guanidine-derived diazetidinones have proven to be even less stable than those derived from amidines (see Section 2.1.2), undergoing rapid retro-[2 + 2] cycloaddition to yield the thermodynamically more stable guanidines and isocyanates. This reactivity can be effectively exploited for the preparation of alkyl- and aryl-substituted isocyanates from readily available tosyl isocyanates. The instability (reactivity) of guanidine-based diazetidinones can be attributed to the influence of the exocyclic nitrogen-based lone pairs (Figure 2).

2.2. Photochemical [2 + 2] Cycloaddition

The synthesis of diazetidinones via [2 + 2] photocycloaddition is directly inspired by the photochemistry of nucleobases in DNA—essentially, by nature itself. When Nishio and co-workers set out to synthesize diazetidinones,^[33] they drew inspiration from the

Scheme 9. A) Reaction of 1.0 equivalent of amidines **45** with 1.0 equivalent of isocyanates **35**. B) Reaction of 2.0 equivalents of isocyanate **35** with 1.0 equivalent of amidines **45**, yielding triazines **47**.

Scheme 10. Selected examples of the reaction between hydrazine-derived aldimines **48** and isocyanates **35**, yielding unexpected zwitterionic compounds **55**.

work of Taylor and others,^[48–50] selecting substituted pyrimidinones as starting materials for a photochemically driven [2 + 2] cycloaddition.

Taylor and his team originally focused on studying the behavior of DNA under UV light (**Scheme 13**).^[48,49] They observed that UV irradiation causes significant damage to DNA nucleobases, triggering intramolecular reactions between adjacent bases and leading to the formation of DNA lesions. Notably, when two neighboring pyrimidine-type bases (such as thymine–thymine, TpT, **65**) are in close proximity, UV-B/C light can initiate a [2 + 2] photocycloaddition, resulting in the formation of a cyclobutane pyrimidine dimer (CPD) (**66**).

Simultaneously, a Paternò–Büchi [2 + 2] cycloaddition can occur, producing an oxetane intermediate (**67**).^[49,50] This unstable intermediate rapidly undergoes a proximity-induced, proton-mediated rearrangement to form a pyrimidinone derivative (**68**), known as a (6–4) photoproduct. These (6–4) lesions can further undergo a 4 π sigmatropic rearrangement, yielding so-called Dewar lesions (**69**), which contain the diazetidone ring structure.

Based on this precedent, Nishio and co-workers investigated the photochemistry of substituted pyrimidinones

Scheme 11. A) Reaction of seven-membered cyclic imine ether **56a** with isocyanates **6**, yielding diazetidinones **57**. Selected examples are shown. B) A plausible explanation for the formation of the observed adduct **58** involves an imine–enamine equilibrium. C) Reaction of five- and six-membered cyclic imine ethers **56c** and **56b**, respectively, with isocyanates **6**. The formation of no desired diazetidinone scaffolds was observed.

(Scheme 14).^[33,51–54] They observed that when pyrimidinones **70** were irradiated in benzene at 300 nm, bicyclic Dewar-type compounds **71** were formed (Scheme 14A).^[53,54] The cyclization reaction proved reversible: at 200 °C or under 254 nm irradiation, bicycles **71** underwent retrocyclization, regenerating the original pyrimidinones **70**. It is also worth noting that no reaction occurred when the experiment was performed with 4-aminopyrimidinones—a cytosine-like analogue of **70** (formation of **71f**).

Further transformations of bicycles **71** into structurally more diverse diazetidinones were subsequently attempted. Pd-mediated hydrogenation of compound **71a** yielded the fully saturated bicycles **72**, which proved stable to retrocycloaddition (Scheme 14B).^[53] However, the ozonolysis of compound **71** in aprotic solvent proved more synthetically valuable, generating diazetidinone aldehydes **73** (Scheme 14C).^[33] When a mixture of CH₂Cl₂ and a protic solvent (MeOH) was employed, the reaction yielded both the aldehyde **73** and cyclic acetal **74** (Scheme 14D).^[33]

From a reactivity standpoint, the transformation potential of bicycles **71** and aldehydes **73** was further explored. Heating

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the spatial orientation of the exocyclic nitrogen lone pair relative to the diazetidinone ring in both spirocyclic and monocyclic frameworks. The illustration highlights the potential destabilization of the diazetidinone ring caused by lone pair–σ*_{C–N} antibonding orbital interactions.

N-aryl-substituted bicycles **71** in benzene resulted in the formation of quinolines **75** (Scheme 15).^[55] Nevertheless, greater synthetic utility lies in further modifications of the aldehyde-functionalized diazetidinones **73**, which can be readily converted into aza-β-lactam analogues^[56]—a topic discussed in greater detail in Section 3, focusing on the biological properties of diazetidinones.

2.3. Transition-Metal-Promoted Insertion Reactions of CO

The first successful synthesis of diazetidinones via transition metal catalysis was reported by Hegedus and Kramer in 1984,^[57,58] who attempted the preparation of 1,2-diazetidiones (**78**) by reacting azobenzene (**77**) with a chromium carbene complex (**76**). This reaction built upon the Hegedus group's earlier work on chromium-mediated metathesis reactions involving heteroatom-stabilized chromium complexes, which had previously enabled the synthesis of β-lactams through the photolytic reaction of chromium carbene **76** with imines (see Scheme 16A).^[59]

Interestingly, when a mixture of chromium carbene **76** and azobenzene **77** in petroleum ether was irradiated with sunlight at 0 °C, an inseparable 1:1 mixture of 1,2-diazetidione (**78**) and 1,3-diazetidione (**79**) was obtained in 31% yield (Scheme 16B). When the reaction was instead irradiated using Vita-Lite fluorescent tubes (emission range: 320–700 nm), the overall yield remained similar (34%), but the product distribution shifted significantly in favor of 1,3-diazetidione **79** (**78:79** = 15:85). Reactions involving electron-rich, unsymmetrical azobenzenes yielded 1,3-diazetidione **79** as the exclusive product, whereas electron-poor, unsymmetrical azobenzenes failed to produce any diazetidinone derivatives (see Scheme 16C). In all cases, however, the imine **80** was observed as the major product.

Scheme 12. Reactions of guanidines with isocyanates. A) Synthesis and isolation of diazetidinones **61a** and **61b**. B) Synthesis of isolable zwitterionic intermediates **64** and their subsequent transformation into guanidine **62**. C) One-pot protocol enabling substitution exchange between tosyl isocyanate **60a** and guanidine **59**.

Scheme 13. UV light-induced formation of DNA lesions between two neighboring pyrimidine-type bases **65**. Upon UV-B/C irradiation, adjacent pyrimidines undergo [2 + 2] photocycloaddition to form CPDs (**66**) or oxetane intermediates **67**. The latter rearrange into (6-4) photoproducts **68**, which can further convert into Dewar isomers **69** through a 4 π sigmatropic shift.

Further mechanistic investigations by Hegedus and Lundmark revealed a complex reaction pathway, with key insights summarized in **Scheme 17**.^[57] A crucial step in the transformation is the *E/Z* isomerization of azobenzene **77**, which is necessary for its reaction with the chromium carbene complex **76**. Once formed, complex **76** can proceed via two distinct pathways: one involving intermediate **81**, governed by thermodynamic control, and the

other via the zwitterionic adduct **83**, which is kinetically favored. Upon irradiation, intermediate **83** can convert into the four-membered species **85**, which may then undergo a metathesis reaction to yield imine **80** and chromium complex **84**. Alternatively, photolysis can lead to the formation of a different zwitterionic intermediate **86**. This species subsequently fragments to complex **87**, which exists in equilibrium with complex **88**. Ultimately,

Scheme 14. A) Biomimetic synthesis of bicyclic strained diazetidinones 71. B) Hydrogenation-based synthetic modifications of diazetidinones 71. C) Synthesis of aldehyde-substituted diazetidinones 73. D) Ozonolysis of diazetidinone 71 in protic solvents: synthesis of bridged ketal 74.

complex **88** gives rise to the observed 1,3-diazetidione **79a**. Notably, when other metal carbene complexes—such as those based on tungsten or molybdenum—were employed in place of chromium, no formation of 1,3-diazetidione **79** was observed. At best, short-lived tungsten-containing analogues of intermediates **83** and **85** were detected.^[60,61]

A decade later, Alper and colleagues reported a straightforward and regioselective carbonyl insertion into the nitrogen–nitrogen bond of diaziridines **89**, leading exclusively to the formation of 1,3-diazetidiones **90** (Scheme 18).^[62] The scope and

Scheme 15. A) Thermal transformation of bicyclic diazetidinones **71** into phenylquinolines **75**—selected examples. B) Proposed reaction mechanism for the conversion of diazetidinone **71** to phenylquinoline **75**.

limitations of this methodology were subsequently investigated, revealing that while the Pd-catalyzed approach proceeds only with 3-monosubstituted diaziridines **89**, cobalt-mediated reactions proceed only when 3,3-disubstituted diaziridines **89** are used as starting materials (Scheme 18). Remarkably, the reaction exhibited pronounced sensitivity to catalyst selection, proceeding exclusively in the presence of catalytic amounts (5 mol%) of Pd(dba)₂. Neither stoichiometric quantities nor alternative catalysts—such as Pd(OAc)₂ or various rhodium(I) salts—proved effective in promoting the transformation.

The proposed mechanism begins with the generation of a Pd_n(CO) species, which coordinates to the less sterically hindered nitrogen atom of diaziridine **89a**. The resulting intermediate **91** undergoes palladium insertion into the adjacent C–H bond. This leads to intermediate **92**, which, with the assistance of an additional equivalent of **89a**, undergoes Pd migration to the nitrogen atom of the diaziridine ring, forming intermediate **94**. This species is primed for nitrogen migration to the carbonyl group. The resulting five-membered palladacycle **95** then undergoes hydride migration, releasing a second equivalent of **89a**, and subsequent Pd reductive elimination furnishes the desired 1,3-diazetidione **90a** (Scheme 19A). However, the precise origin of the unique catalytic activity of Pd(dba)₂ remains unclear.

Interestingly, the reaction also proceeds in the presence of a stoichiometric amount (2.0 equiv) of cobalt catalyst, consistent with the proposed mechanism for the cobalt-mediated transformation (Scheme 19B). According to this mechanism, diaziridine **89d** reacts with CO₂(CO)₈ at the less hindered nitrogen atom to form complex **96**. The coordinated cobalt then inserts into

A. Aza-β-lactam synthesis and a proposed approach to 1,2-diazetidiones

B. Observed reaction outcome

C. Reaction scope – main product shown

Scheme 16. Synthesis of 1,3-diazetidiones **79** via carbonyl Insertion. A) Proposed synthesis of aza-β-lactams via the reaction of chromium carbenes with azobenzene. B) Summary of products obtained from the photochemical reaction between chromium carbene complex **76** and azobenzene **77**, along with reaction condition optimization. C) Assessment of substrate scope and overall reaction applicability.

the N–N bond, generating the four-membered intermediate **97**, which undergoes intramolecular ligand migration to yield the more stable five-membered intermediate **98**. Reductive elimination from this species releases the desired 1,3-diazetidione **90d**.

It is worth noting that both of these transformations have remained largely underexplored and have not been previously exploited in the synthesis of 1,3-diazetidiones.

3. Biological Activity

Interest in 1,3-diazetidion-2-ones dates back to the early 1990s, when Nangia and co-workers began investigating novel

Scheme 17. Proposed reaction mechanism and rationalization formation pathways of 1,2-diazetidiones **78**, 1,3-diazetidiones **79**, and imine **80**, as proposed by Hegedus and Lundmark.^[57]

Scheme 18. Scope and limitations of transition metal-catalyzed carbonyl insertion into the N–N bond of diaziridines **89**. Selective synthesis of 1,3-diazetidiones **90**.

β-lactam analogues as potential solutions to the growing problem of antibiotic resistance.^[23,24] Their AM1-based computational study focused on identifying potent inhibitors of β-lactamases and transpeptidases.^[25] One of the key outcomes of this work was the identification of 1,3-diazetidion-2-ones as promising members of a broader class of compounds known as aza-β-lactams.

Their study suggested that bicyclic 1,3-diazetidion-2-one derivatives are particularly attractive due to their predicted stability and the presence of a highly electrophilic carbonyl group (Scheme 20). This carbonyl is capable of interacting with β-lactamases, as the 1,3-diazetidion-2-one scaffold is isosteric with traditional β-lactams. From a conceptual standpoint, the advantage of 1,3-diazetidion-2-one derivatives over conventional β-lactams lies in the step following interaction with the active site of β-lactamase. When β-lactamase from resistant bacteria

Scheme 19. A) Proposed reaction mechanism for Pd-catalyzed 1,3-diazetidione formation. B) Proposed reaction mechanism for stoichiometric $\text{CO}_2(\text{CO})_8$ -mediated 1,3-diazetidione formation.

attacks a β -lactam compound such as **99**, it forms intermediate **100**. However, due to resistance-associated mutations, the resulting ester bond can be hydrolyzed, regenerating the active enzyme.

In contrast, when the analogous 1,3-diazetidione **102** is targeted by β -lactamase, the reaction leads to intermediate **103a**, in which the enzyme becomes covalently bound to the opened diazetidione ring via a carbamoyl linkage. This

intermediate is better represented by its resonance form **103b**, which highlights the stability of the carbamoyl bond and its reduced susceptibility to hydrolysis.

Independently, Coll and co-workers arrived at similar conclusions during their theoretical investigation of β -lactams and their unnatural analogues—namely aza-, oxo-, and thio- β -lactams—using the PM3 semiempirical method.^[63,64] Their findings were consistent with those of Nangia, as they demonstrated that the incorporation of an additional nitrogen atom into the four-membered ring imparts unique electronic properties, resulting in enhanced—and potentially irreversible— inhibition of β -lactamases. The study concluded that the behavior of aza- β -lactams closely resembles that of clavulanic acid, positioning them as promising alternatives to conventional β -lactam antibiotics.

Based on this hypothesis, Nangia and co-workers synthesized 1,3-diazetidione **73** using Nishio's photochemical [2 + 2]-cycloaddition followed by ozone-mediated ring opening.^[52,53] This compound was subsequently modified to yield a variety of bicyclic and monocyclic 1,3-diazetidione derivatives (selected examples shown in **Scheme 21A**). A library of these compounds was prepared and evaluated for biological activity against the Gram-positive bacterium *Bacillus subtilis* (selected examples shown in **Scheme 21B**). Notably, several of the synthesized compounds—particularly the bicyclic derivatives **111** and **112**—exhibited stronger inhibitory activity than the reference antibiotic ampicillin, which served as a positive control in these assays. However, since antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains were not included in the evaluation, the original hypothesis could not be conclusively confirmed.

Since 2024, several studies have reported the preliminary evaluation of antioxidant, antifungal, antibacterial, and anticancer activities of 1,3-diazetidione-2-ones synthesized via the well-established [2 + 2] cycloaddition of aromatic imines with phenyl or naphthyl isocyanates (**Figure 3**).^[65–67] Among the extensive library of compounds investigated, several derivatives demonstrated promising bioactivity. However, further studies are necessary to validate and expand upon these findings, as well as to elucidate the underlying mechanisms of action.

Scheme 20. Inactivation of β -lactamase by β -lactam antibiotics (top) and by 1,3-diazetidione-2-ones derivatives such as **102** (bottom).

Scheme 21. A) An example of the bicyclic and monocyclic 1,3-diazetid-2-one derivatives synthesis that starts from the readily available 1,3-diazetid-2-one 73. B) Biological evaluation of selected 1,3-diazetid-2-one derivatives against *Bacillus subtilis* at a concentration of 330 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$. Percentage inhibition is shown. TBS = *tert*-butyldimethylsilyl.

Figure 3. Selected recently evaluated 1,3-diazetid-2-ones with reported anticancer (113),^[65] antioxidant (114),^[66] and antimicrobial/fungal activity (115).^[67] The results are based on preliminary assays and require further validation. The antimicrobial activity assays was conducted using standard agar diffusion techniques, where compound-impregnated discs were placed on inoculated agar plates. Zones of inhibition were measured qualitatively to assess antimicrobial efficacy. While this approach provided an initial indication of bioactivity, it did not allow for precise quantification of minimum inhibitory concentrations.

4. Summary and Outlook

1,3-diazetid-2-ones represent a structurally intriguing and pharmacologically promising subclass of aza- β -lactams. Despite their conceptual appeal as β -lactam analogues with the potential to overcome β -lactamase-mediated resistance, their broader development has been significantly constrained by synthetic limitations. The predominant [2 + 2] cycloaddition strategy, while foundational, suffers from high substrate dependency, susceptibility to side reactions, and cycloreversion, all of which restrict the accessibility of the target compounds.

Alternative synthetic approaches—including photochemical and transition-metal-catalyzed methods—have shown encouraging results but remain underdeveloped and often lack general applicability. A major limitation across most reported strategies is the requirement for aromatic substitution on the nitrogen atoms of the 1,3-diazetid-2-one core, which narrows the scope of accessible derivatives.

From a biological perspective, both computational and experimental studies have consistently underscored the potential of 1,3-diazetid-2-ones as β -lactamase inhibitors and antimicrobial agents. Their unique properties, particularly the formation of hydrolysis-resistant carbamoyl-enzyme intermediates, offer a compelling mechanism to circumvent established resistance pathways. Recent findings also suggest broader therapeutic potential, including antioxidant and anticancer activities.

Nevertheless, the full pharmacological promise of 1,3-diazetid-2-ones remains largely untapped. To unlock this potential, future research must prioritize the development of novel synthetic methodologies that enable access to non- N,N' -diaryl derivatives. Such advances would facilitate systematic biological evaluation of structurally diverse analogues, enabling the identification of key pharmacophores and optimization of bioactivity. In this context, the exploration of synthetic strategies beyond [2 + 2] cycloaddition and transition metal-mediated carbonyl insertion is particularly urgent. Of these, the latter remains especially underexplored and may offer greater flexibility for innovation.

In summary, while 1,3-diazetid-2-ones remain an underutilized scaffold, their distinctive structural and electronic features position them as valuable candidates in the ongoing search for novel therapeutics. With renewed synthetic innovation, this class of compounds holds significant promise for future advances in medicinal chemistry.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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